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APPLICATION OF CA- MARKOV CHAIN MODEL IN LANDUSE/LAND COVER PROJECTION IN SOUTHERN PART OF GOMBE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: Human activities such as intensive farming, deforestation, logging, and urban development are significantly impacting land use and cover, posing major environmental sustainability challenges, especially in areas experiencing rapid population growth and urbanization. Based on the status of Land Use Land Cover (LULC) of the reference year 2017 in Southern part of Gombe, this study sought to predict future changes in land use/cover for 2030, 2040 and 2050 projected years with the application of CA-Markov chain model. Kappa index was used to validate the model, and the overall accuracy recorded 93.91%. After calibration and validation of the model, LULC was predicted and the result revealed that rock outcrop was projected to decrease from 337.06sqkm in 2017 to 285.33sqkm, 200.35sqkm and 108.33sqkm in 2030, 2040 and 2050 respectively. Vegetation cover which recorded 1622.07sqkm in 2017 is projected to decrease to 1356.59sqkm, 1032.92sqkm and 707.03sqkm in 2030, 2040 and 2050 while area covered by bare surfaces which was 2210.52sqkm in 2017 is projected to increase to 2513.36sqkm, 2904.42sqkm and 3302.47sqkm for 2030, 2040 and 2050 respectively. Settlement which is 67.56sqkm in 2017 is also projected to increase to 81.63sqkm, 99.22sqkm and 119.08sqkm in 2030, 2040 and 2050 respectively. In conclusion, the CA-Markov model's accurate projections of future land use and cover changes reveal an alarming trend of declining vegetation and increasing bare surfaces, emphasizing the urgent need for sustainable land management such as reforestation, afforestation and other conservation practices to preserve vegetation cover as well as continuous monitoring of LULC changes using advanced remote sensing technologies and modeling techniques.

Keywords: CA-Markov, Changes, Kappa Index, Landuse/Landcover, Projection

INTRODUCTION

Land use and land cover (LULC) changes have become a central focus in environmental studies due to their significant impacts on ecosystem services, biodiversity, and human livelihoods. Roy *et al.* (2016) noted that LULC changes due to human activities are responsible for the observed, increase in irreversible negative impact on global environmental

systems. Globally, changes in land use patterns driven by urbanization, agricultural expansion, deforestation, and other anthropogenic activities are recognized as major contributors to environmental degradation and climate change (Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2019; Verburg *et al.*, 2019). In developing regions like Nigeria, these changes are particularly pronounced, leading to severe consequences such as habitat loss, soil erosion, and water

resource depletion (Oyinloye and Olaniyi, 2020). The ability to monitor, analyze and predict these changes are crucial for formulating policies that promote sustainable development and environmental conservation.

The Southern part of Gombe State, Nigeria, is a region experiencing rapid population growth and urbanization, which have intensified pressures on its natural resources. The area's diverse landscape, which includes savannas, forests, and agricultural lands, is undergoing significant transformations due to both natural processes and human activities (Echendu, 2021; Michael, 2022). These transformations have led to concerns about the long-term sustainability of the region's ecosystems and the livelihoods of its inhabitants. The importance of assessing, monitoring and modeling the past, present and future LULC conditions using modern simulation and analytical tools cannot be overemphasized in view of the recurrence of natural disasters across the globe (Rimal *et al.*, 2018). Understanding the spatial and temporal dynamics of LULC changes in Southern part of Gombe is therefore essential for developing effective land management strategies that balance environmental protection with socio-economic development.

Remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) provide powerful tools for analyzing LULC changes over time. These technologies allow for the integration of spatial data from multiple time periods, enabling the identification of trends and patterns in land use dynamics (Singh *et al.*, 2015). Among the various models available for LULC analysis, the Cellular Automata-Markov (CA-Markov) model has emerged as one of the most effective for simulating future land use scenarios based on historical data. The CA-Markov model combines the strengths of cellular automata, which captures the spatial structure and

neighborhood interactions of land use changes, with the Markov chain process, which models the probabilities of land cover transitions over time (Mas *et al.*, 2014; Aburas *et al.*, 2016).

The application of the CA-Markov model in LULC studies has been widely documented, with successful implementations across various geographic regions. For instance, in the Duhok district of Iraq, Abdulrahman and Ameen (2020) utilized the CA-Markov model to predict LULC changes between 1999 and 2033, providing critical insights into urban expansion and its environmental impacts. Similarly, Mohamed and Worku (2020) applied the model in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, to simulate urban land use dynamics, highlighting the potential of the CA-Markov model to inform urban planning and policy development. These studies demonstrate the model's robustness and versatility, making it a valuable tool for LULC analysis in diverse environmental contexts.

In this study, the CA-Markov model was employed to predict future LULC changes in Southern part of Gombe State, Nigeria, for the years 2030, 2040, and 2050. The study used LULC maps from 2006 and 2017 as baseline data to generate transition probabilities and simulate future scenarios. The objective was to provide a comprehensive understanding of the likely trajectories of land use changes in the region, which can inform land management strategies aimed at mitigating environmental degradation and promoting sustainable development. By integrating spatial analysis with predictive modeling, this research sought to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on LULC dynamics in Nigeria. The findings will be particularly relevant for policymakers, environmental managers, and stakeholders involved in land use planning and natural resource management in Gombe State and similar regions. As the pressures on land

resources continue to mount, the need for reliable tools to anticipate and manage land use changes becomes increasingly urgent. This study aims to address this need by offering a detailed analysis of potential future LULC scenarios, thereby supporting efforts to achieve sustainable land management and environmental conservation in the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

THE STUDY AREA

The Southern part of Gombe is positioned between latitudes $9^{\circ}35'0''\text{N}$ and $10^{\circ}07'0''\text{N}$ and longitudes $11^{\circ}00'0''\text{E}$ and $11^{\circ}50'0''\text{E}$ (Figure 1). Covering an area of approximately $4,257.67\text{km}^2$ (Michael, 2022), this region exhibits a varied topography with rolling hills, expansive plains, and scattered valleys. The area is situated in the Sudan savanna region and it is drained by the Gongola River and its tributaries (Ikusemoran, et al., 2018). The climate is tropical with high temperatures and

distinct wet and dry seasons which significantly impacts its agricultural practices and land use. The region features diverse soils, including dominant sandy loam, clay loam in valleys, and sandy soils in drier areas. Despite being fertile, these soils are erosion-prone due to heavy rainfall (Ikusemoran, et al, 2016). The area's Sudan savanna landscape encompasses grasslands with scattered trees and shrubs such as; *Adansonia digitata*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Phoenix dactytera* *Acacia senegal* amongst other woodlands in valleys, and bushlands in drier zones (Abu et. al., 2022).

The region is predominantly rural, with a mix of traditional farming communities and emerging urban centers. Agriculture is a major economic activity, but it is increasingly challenged by issues such as deforestation and land degradation.

Figure 1: The Study Area

Source: Modified from Nigeria Geological Survey Agency, (2022)

METHODOLOGY

This study combined remote sensing, Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques, and the Cellular Automata-Markov (CA-Markov) model to monitor and predict future Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) changes in the Southern part of Gombe State, Nigeria. Satellite images from Landsat for the years 2006 and 2017 were acquired from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer platform, selected for their moderate spatial resolution of 30 meters. The images underwent preprocessing steps, including radiometric, geometric, and atmospheric corrections, to enhance accuracy and ensure alignment with the study area's geographic coordinates. These preprocessed images were then classified into various LULC categories using a supervised classification approach with the Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) algorithm in ArcGIS 10.8 software. The classification's accuracy was assessed through a confusion matrix ensuring reliability for subsequent analysis.

Following the classification, the CA-Markov model was calibrated using the LULC maps from 2006 and 2017. The model's calibration involved generating transition probability matrices, which estimate the likelihood of LULC transitions over time, and transition suitability maps created using the Multi-Criteria Evaluation (MCE) module in IDRISI Selva software. These maps integrate factors such as road proximity, elevation, and slope to assess the suitability of land for different uses. The calibrated model was then used to simulate future LULC scenarios for the years 2030, 2040, and 2050, predicting changes in land use based on current trends. These simulations were validated by comparing the predicted 2017 LULC map with the actual map, using the Kappa index to measure agreement and confirm the model's accuracy.

The validation process revealed a strong agreement between the simulated and actual LULC maps, with a Kappa value of 93.91%, indicating the model's robustness in predicting future changes. The projected LULC maps for 2030, 2040, and 2050 were analyzed to identify trends and quantify changes in land use classes, such as vegetation, bare surfaces, and settlements. This methodology, utilizing advanced GIS and modeling tools like ArcGIS 10.8 and IDRISI Selva, provides a comprehensive approach to understanding and predicting land use dynamics in southern part of Gombe State, offering crucial insights for sustainable land management and planning in the region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LAND USE AND LAND COVER (LULC) CLASSIFICATION RESULTS

The classification of LULC based on satellite imagery from 2006 and 2017, revealed substantial changes in land use patterns. The analysis in Table 1, categorized the study area into five primary LULC types: vegetation, bare surfaces, rock outcrops, water bodies, and settlements. In 2006, vegetation was the dominant class, covering 50.34% of the total area. By 2017, this had decreased slightly to 38.10%, reflecting ongoing environmental stressors such as deforestation and land conversion for agriculture. Conversely, bare surfaces increased from 38.11% in 2006 to 51.92% in 2017. This trend indicates significant land degradation and expansion of agricultural activities, which are consistent with similar studies of Adamu (2019) and Yusuf et al. (2021). The high classification accuracy as confirmed by the confusion matrix and Kappa coefficient supports the reliability of these LULC maps for further analysis and modeling.

Table 1: Comparison of actual and simulated LULC changes in 2017

Class	2006		2017 actual		2017 Simulated		Changes	
	Area(km ²)	%	Area(km ²)	%	Area(km ²)	%	RC	PC
Rock Outcrop	416.41	9.78	337.06	7.92	336.15	7.90	-0.9	-0.3
Vegetation	2143.46	50.34	1622.07	38.10	1623.44	38.13	1.4	0.1
Bare Surfaces	1622.59	38.11	2210.52	51.92	2210.36	51.91	-0.2	0.0
Waterbody	22.85	0.54	20.46	0.48	20.06	0.47	-0.4	-2.0
Settlement	52.36	1.23	67.56	1.59	67.66	1.59	0.1	0.1
Total	4257.67	100.00	4257.67	100.00	4257.67	100.00		

Note. PC = percentage of change, and RC = rate of change.

Source: Author’s Analysis, (2022)

CA-MARKOV MODEL SIMULATION AND VALIDATION

The CA-Markov model was used to project future LULC scenarios for 2030, 2040, and 2050, utilizing the transition probabilities derived from the 2006 and 2017 LULC maps. The validation process, outlined in Table 2, demonstrates the CA-Markov model with an overall Kappa value of 93.91%. This high Kappa value indicates a strong agreement between the simulated and actual LULC maps for 2017, validating the model's predictive capability. The transition probability matrices illustrated in Figure 2,

and the transition suitability maps were essential in calibrating the model, integrating factors such as road proximity, elevation, and slope as noted in Camara, (2020) and Mohamed and Worku, (2020). The projected LULC maps for 2030, 2040 and 2050 presented in Figures 3, 4, and 5 respectively shows the model’s ability to simulate changes in land cover over time. The validation results align with findings from Bello et al (2018) and Pontius Jr and Schneider, (2001) confirming the model's accuracy in predicting future land use changes.

Figure 2: Model constraints and factors and Result from Idrisi Selva V.17

Source: Author’s Analysis, (2022)

Table 2: Statistical validation of the CA-Markov chain model.

Statistics	Value
Kstandard	0.95304
Klocation	0.99827
Klocationstrata	0.95469
Overall K	93.90798

Source: Author’s Analysis, (2022)

Figure 3: 2030 LULC projection
Source: Author’s field survey (2022)

Figure 4: 2040 LULC Projection
Source: Author’s field survey (2022)

Figure 5: 2050 LULC Projection
Source: Author’s field survey (2022)

PROJECTED LAND USE LAND COVER CHANGES FOR 2030, 2040, AND 2050

The projections for 2030, 2040, and 2050 indicate substantial changes in vegetal cover in Southern part of Gombe as shown in Table 3 and Figures 6, 7 and 8. The area covered by vegetation is expected to decline significantly, from 38.10% in 2017 to 31.86% by 2030, further decreasing to 24.26% by 2040, and 16.61% by 2050. This trend reflects a continued loss of forested areas due to deforestation and land degradation. In contrast, the area covered by bare surfaces is projected to increase from 51.92% in 2017 to 59.03% in 2030 and would further expand to 68.22% by 2040, and 77.57% by 2050. This increase is indicative of extensive land degradation and the conversion of natural landscapes into agricultural or urban areas as noted in the works of Abdulrahman and Ameen, (2020).

The expansion of settlements is also notable, with projections showing a growth from 1.92% in 2030 to 2.80% by 2050, reflecting urbanization pressures in the region. Figures 9 and 10 illustrate these changes and highlight the need for effective land management strategies to address the projected trends.

Table 3: Projection of LULC area change (sqkm) from 2017 to 2050

Class	Actual		Projected									
	2017		2030		2040		2050		2030-2040		2040-2050	
	Area	%	Area	%	Area	%	Area	%	RC(km ²)	PC	RC(km ²)	PC
Rock outcrop	337.06	7.92	285.33	6.70	200.35	4.71	108.33	2.54	-84.98	-29.78	-92.02	-45.93
Vegetation	1622.07	38.10	1356.59	31.86	1032.92	24.26	707.03	16.61	-323.67	-23.86	-325.89	-31.55
Bare surfaces	2210.52	51.92	2513.36	59.03	2904.42	68.22	3302.47	77.57	391.06	15.56	398.05	13.70
Water bodies	20.46	0.48	20.76	0.49	20.76	0.49	20.76	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Settlement	67.56	1.59	81.63	1.92	99.22	2.33	119.08	2.80	17.59	21.55	19.86	20.02
Total	4257.67	100.00	4257.67	100.00	4257.67	100.00	4257.67	100.00				

Note. PC = percentage of change, and RC = rate of change.

Source: Author's Analysis (2022)

Figure 6: Projected Vegetation Cover 2030
Source: Author's field survey (2022)

Figure 7: Vegetation cover 2040 Projected
Source: Author's field survey (2022)

Figure 8: Vegetation 2050 Projected
Source: Author’s field survey (2022)

Figure 9: Projected Changes 2030 to 2040
Source: Author’s Analysis (2022)

Figure 10: Projected changes 2040 to 2050
Source: Author's Analysis (2022)

IMPLICATIONS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

The projected LULC and Vegetation changes have significant implications for environmental resource management in Southern part of Gombe. The decline in vegetation cover and the increase in bare surfaces are likely to exacerbate soil erosion, reduce biodiversity, and increase vulnerability to climate change impacts (Mbaya et al., (2022)). The loss of vegetation can lead to diminished ecosystem services, such as carbon sequestration and water regulation, which are critical for maintaining environmental health (Michael, 2022; Mbaya et. al., 2022). The expansion of settlements and agricultural areas further pressures land resources, necessitating comprehensive land use planning and sustainable development practices. Integrating these projections into regional planning frameworks can help mitigate the adverse

effects of land degradation and support environmental conservation efforts.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis of LULC from 2006 to 2017 revealed a significant shift from vegetation to bare surfaces, indicative of ongoing land degradation and increased agricultural activities. The CA-Markov model, used to project future LULC scenarios for 2030, 2040, and 2050, demonstrated robust predictive capability, with high validation accuracy. The projections indicate a continued decline in vegetation cover and an expansion of bare surfaces which underscores the pressing need for effective land management and conservation strategies. The results highlight the interplay between natural processes and anthropogenic pressures, emphasizing the urgency of integrating environmental considerations into regional planning. The projected trends underscore the importance of

proactive environmental management to mitigate adverse impacts. Based on the findings, the study recommends as follows:

1. It is crucial to adopt sustainable land management practices such as reforestation, afforestation and sustainable agricultural techniques to restore and preserve vegetation cover.
2. Land Use Planning should integrate the projections from this study to guide land use decisions. Developing land use policies that balance development with environmental conservation can help mitigate the adverse effects of urbanization and agricultural expansion.
3. Continuous monitoring of LULC changes using advanced remote sensing technologies and modeling techniques

is essential for assessing the effectiveness of implemented strategies and making informed decisions.

4. Engaging local communities in conservation efforts and raising awareness about the impact of land use changes can foster collective action towards sustainable land management. Educational programs can help communities understand the importance of preserving natural resources and adopting environmentally friendly practices.
5. Further research is needed to explore the underlying causes of LULC changes and their broader impacts on the environment and society. Supporting research and developing evidence-based policies can drive more effective interventions and strategies for managing land resources.

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